

D5.2 Co-Change Project Website

Version 1.0

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Dissemination Level: public

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Peer-reviewed by:

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Introduction

This report describes activities carried out by ESSRG and consortium partners for the completion of Task 5.2 of the Co-Change project: a project website as a tool for external communication. The deliverable for this task is an actual project webpage (<http://www.cochangeproject.eu/>) followed by this documentation.

ESSRG, as a responsible partner for the development, identified three main functionalities that the website could perform.

1. **Support:** Change Labs will be invited to present their insights and results as well as local contextual challenges faced during the implementation.
2. **Dissemination:** project partners and stakeholders will report about their Co-Change project experience and the desired changes needed in RFOs and RPOs, encouraging the streamlining of responsible research practices
3. **Sharing:** Co-Change partners and stakeholders will share what they learn from each other in new partnerships in the "quadruple helix."

The website has a responsive web design with six different subpage types, search engine and administration with CMS. The website will enable Co-Change to present its approach towards changes necessary for mainstreaming responsible research practices in relevant formats for research funding organisations (RFOs) and research performing organisations (RPOs). The main topics that this work will entail will be handled through quickly searchable *tags*, such as, e.g. *citizen science, extended peer review, co-creation, agenda-setting, co-production, co-evaluation, research ethics, open access, citizens' engagement, gender equality, science education*.

The main targets of the website are research organisations and research funding organisations their management and researchers, the project stakeholders, and expert organisations. The expected number of visits is 3.000 for the entire duration of the project. For that impact measurement, we installed Google Analytics to track the number of visitors.

In all other social media aspects, the consortium partners decided that Co-Change will not establish and manage project-level accounts or groups (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter), but invite partners to create project related posts through using the **#COCHANGE2020** hashtag, which is EU's hashtag for the project.

Design and registration data

The web-designer is Mr Balázs Sipos, ESSRG, and the web developer is SKAPE.IO KFT.

WHOIS Domain information is officially represented by <http://www.eurid.eu>.
The registration data is available at whois.net as below:

Your Domain Starting Place...
 Type here for whois, domain and keyword results

WHOIS LOOKUP

cochangeproject.eu is already registered*

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 % WHOIS cochangeproject.eu
 Domain: cochangeproject.eu
 Script: LATEX
 Registrar: NOT DISCLOSED
 Web: www.eurid.eu for webbased WHOIS
 On-site(): NOT DISCLOSED
 Web: www.eurid.eu for webbased WHOIS
 Registrar: Name: GoDaddy.com, LLC
 Website: http://www.godaddy.com
 Name servers: ns67.domaincontrol.com
 ns67.domaincontrol.com
 Please visit www.eurid.eu for more info.

Popular

<input type="checkbox"/>	cochangeproject.cc	\$29.99
<input type="checkbox"/>	cochangeproject.ink	\$12.99
<input type="checkbox"/>	cochangeproject.com	\$12.99
<input type="checkbox"/>	cochangeproject.net	\$15.49

BUY SELECTED

Filters

- Popular
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- Media and Music
- Organizations
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- Professional
- Real Estate
- Services
- Shopping
- Sports and Hobbies
- Trades and Construction
- Travel and Tourism

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Screenshots of the project website

MENU 00: HOME

Static content

Short general description of the project and mixed content blocks from the other subpages. The content is mostly static, except for the linked dynamic content (e.g. latest news or events) – no CMS (*content management system*) is needed. Functional elements on the page: search bar, social media links.

MENU 01: ABOUT

Static content

General description of the project itself. Introduction of the partners (100-150 characters per each) and link to the partners' websites.

CO-CHANGE ABOUT NEWS & EVENTS CHANGE LABS OUTCOMES

WHO WE ARE? WHAT IS RRI? WORK PACKAGES
PARTNERS SOUNDING BOARD
WHO DO WE WANT TO REACH? THE CHANGE LABS

Ethical and responsible conduct in research and innovation is key to transform science-society relations. It implies that societal actors (researchers, citizens, policymakers, businesses and third-sector organisations) work together during the whole research and innovation process. The aim is to align both the process and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society.

The EU-funded Co-Change project will apply an innovative systemic approach to boost the transformative capacity and leadership for responsible research. It will centre on the concept of change labs and focus on interactions and dependencies of actors in each research and innovation ecosystem. The project activates change coalitions around each lab, paying particular attention to interactions and dependencies of actors in each R&I ecosystem, since research performing (RPOs) and research funding (RFDOs) organisations co-evolve in and with the R&I ecosystems they are embedded in.

By implementing change labs in their ecosystems, we generate transformative capacity for change in terms of practices, procedures, rules and norms at the individual, organisational and system levels. The outcomes of all change labs will be analysed to produce a toolbox and field book for responsible research related changes which will be broadly disseminated by committed multipliers, including our Sounding Board with experienced responsible research project coordinators and our Advisory Board with quadruple helix partners for further reach. To widen our impact, we publish a call for innovative responsible research practices, inviting more European organizations to Co-Change activities.

CO-CHANGE ABOUT NEWS & EVENTS CHANGE LABS OUTCOMES

WP1 WP2 WP3 WP4 WP5 WP6

Building on prior knowledge and experience through a stock-taking exercise, WP1 provides a solid foundation for the creation of responsible research practices, leveraging the expertise of the consortium, associated partners and advisors towards understanding responsible research 2.0. We will take stock of previous responsible research projects that feeds into all other work packages while fostering a common understanding and language among project partners. The envisaged ecosystem analysis aims at exploring the needs and challenges for the co-creation of changes.

ADVISORY BOARD

Prof. Erik Fisher
ARIZONA STATE UNIVERSITY, USA

Dr. Eric Klemp
CEO OF THE AM CENTRE

Dr. Justine Lacey
COMMONWEALTH SCIENTIFIC AND INDUSTRIAL RESEARCH ORGANISATION

Prof. Barbara Prainsack
UNIVERSITY OF VIENNA, AUSTRIA

Charlotte Alber
AUSTRIAN RESEARCH PROMOTION AGENCY, FFG

MENU 02: CHANGE LABS

Static content

General description of the idea of "change labs" + introduction of each change lab in maximum 2000 characters.

The screenshot shows the CO-CHANGE website interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for ABOUT, NEWS & EVENTS, CHANGE LABS, and OUTCOMES. Below the menu is a map of Europe with several countries highlighted in orange, indicating the locations of change labs. Below the map is a horizontal list of buttons for each change lab: AIT, WWTF, TECNALIA, UNS, CTR, VTT, TU, and NEN. Below the buttons, there is a paragraph defining change labs as organisational spaces for building transformative capacity and leadership in the areas of citizen engagement, science education, gender equality, research ethics and open science through concerted actions of pioneering coalitions of R&I actors. A second paragraph states that change labs share broadly and widely their experience and knowledge beyond their own action research system via the change forum superstructure. At the bottom of the page, there is a row of logos for the participating institutions: ESSRG, TU Delft, tecnia, WWTF, AIT, VTT, and PIRKANMAA.

MENU 03: NEWS (AND EVENTS)

Dynamic content with CMS

Mixed media (picture, text, video) blog-like dynamic page. Each content can be tagged – it can be used to filter the news. All news pieces are integrated with social media sharing icons. Separate templates for events and news.

Project on legal, ethical and social consequences of research and innovation launched

The project Co-Create Change in Research Funding and Performing Organisations (CO-CHANGE) has been launched. Our mission is to support the implementation of changes in research and innovation (R&I) organisations in the areas of research ethics, open access, citizen engagement, gender equality and science education.

Date: 2020. 08. 19.
Location:

NEWS EVENTS

2020. 09. 23. Co-Change Lab Forum in September

0001. 01. 01. Co-Change mission

2020. 09. 23. | Helsinki

Co-Change Lab Forum in September

Aim & Objectives / Europe is working on an ambitious strategy to ensure prosperity, livability and well-being for all. Research and Innovation play a vital role in this, and the Co-Change project aims to make its contribution. You are cordially invited to participate in the first Co-Change Forum on September 23 and 24, 2020. Meet other Labs, Sounding and Advisory Boards and explore the next steps at the Co-Change Forum 1. Together we will define the next steps on making change happen. The objectives for Forum 1 are:

- A Co-Change RRI Vision 2035 based on common Lab themes.
- Each Co-Change Labs has its goals, tasks and a roadmap for next implementation steps in hand.
- Each Co-Change Lab is familiar with the topics and directions of the other Labs.

The Co-Change Forum is implemented as a learning space for all Co-Change Labs. A trust-based cooperation and learning culture among all participants has been established. Preparatory steps towards the next Co-Change Forum have been taken.

Dates & Times / Co-Change Forum 1 will take place on 23 September 2020, 08:30 - 13:00 CET and 24 September 2020, 08:30 - 13:15 CET.

Setting & Agenda / The Forum was planned to take place in Helsinki hosted by partner VTT but due to the circumstances will now go virtual. We plan on using a web-based conferencing solution which AIT successfully used for the International Sustainability Transitions Conference last week. The setting up has started, and we aim to open it for official registration early September. You will be notified in due time. For Forum 1, we have put together an agenda with many different elements and creative methods, all designed to support the work of the Co-Change Labs directly or indirectly.

Day 1 - 23 September

08:30 - Testing conferencing facility - Plenary

09:00 - Welcome and Setting the Scene | 30 min - Plenary

09:30 - Keynote on RRI sensemaking (Mika Nieminen, invited) | 30 min - Plenary

10:15 - Co-Change THEMES - Visioning / part 1 | 65 min - Break-out

MENU 04: OUTCOMES

Dynamic content with CMS and file management system on the backend side

04.1: Deliverables

All the public deliverables in downloadable pdf format.

04.2: Publications

Published articles related to the project.

FOOTER

Static content

Contact options with a *mail-to* link and social media links
Obligatory disclaimer about funding

The screenshot shows the footer of the Co-Change website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Co-Change logo and links for ABOUT, NEWS & EVENTS, CHANGE LABS, and OUTCOMES. Below this is a green banner with the text: "creating tailor-made responsible research related tools and practices. By doing so, we can learn from our work with the stakeholders and engage in change from bottom up scenarios." and a button labeled "MORE ABOUT CHANGE LABS".

The main content area is titled "OUTCOMES" and features three cards, each with a green paper-cut style graphic and a blue base. The cards are labeled: "D7.1 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN DELIVERABLE", "D5.1 PLAN DELIVERABLE", and "D2.1 GUIDELINES DELIVERABLE". Below these cards is a button labeled "MORE OUTCOMES".

The footer contains a row of partner logos: ESSRG, TU Delft, tecnalia, WOTIF, AIT, VTT, and PIRKANMAA. Below the logos is a disclaimer: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 873112. The views expressed on this section are the sole responsibility of their authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission". At the bottom, there is a copyright notice: "© 2020 Co-Change - All Rights Reserved" and links for "Impressum | Privacy Policy" along with social media icons for email and Twitter.